

UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL DE MARINGÁ
Department of Informatics
4080/1 – Experimental Software Engineering (ESE)

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The study to be conducted will consist of an evaluation of the DCEP-SE metadata editor, a tool developed to support the registration and organization of metadata for Software Engineering experiments based on the Dublin Core standard. The purpose of the study is to investigate users' perceptions regarding the use of the tool, considering aspects related to technology acceptance and usability.

Initially, participants will have access to introductory materials containing information about the Dublin Core standard, the concept of metadata editors, and a reference experiment that will serve as the scenario for interaction with the tool. A user guide will also be provided, containing instructions on the editor's main functionalities and on the process of completing the experimental information.

After this familiarization stage, participants will be asked to interact with the DCEP-SE editor by registering information and metadata related to the presented experiment. At the end of the interaction, a questionnaire will be administered to collect participants' perceptions of the tool.

The evaluation will address technology acceptance aspects based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), considering dimensions such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and behavioral intention to use. In addition, a usability assessment will be conducted through the application of the System Usability Scale (SUS).

Through this study, it is expected to gain a better understanding of how potential users evaluate the editor in the context of documenting Software Engineering experiments, as well as to identify opportunities for improving the tool and gather evidence regarding its practical applicability.